

European Fuel Cells and Hydrogen

PIERO LUNGI CONFERENCE

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

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ATENA
FUTURE TECHNOLOGY

Italian National Agency for New Technologies,
Energy and Sustainable Economic Development

Università degli Studi
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European Fuel Cells and Hydrogen

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Proceedings

OF THE 11TH EUROPEAN FUEL CELL PIERO LUNGI CONFERENCE

To Piero Lunghi. We miss you a lot. To you our gratitude for ever.

This book is dedicated to the memory of Piero Lunghi, creator of the European Fuel Cell Technology and Applications Conference, dear friend and colleague, who prematurely passed away in a car accident on damned November 9, 2007.

Piero made significant contributions in the field of fuel cells in the course of his too short career. He was the leading figure in the formation of the fuel cell research group at the University of Perugia and several activities and research projects initiated by him are still ongoing.

This means that, thanks to Piero, many young people are working in this exciting research field and are coming to Naples to present their results. Therefore, Piero's memory is in the conference name but Piero's contribution is still in the contents of this book.

The memory of our friend Piero, his great personal generosity and energy, survives in our hearts, his contribution and his tenacity survive in the work of young people who carry on his vision throughout the world.

Give them your passion, your strength, and make all necessary effort to realize them. There is no greater satisfaction than seeing one's ideas become reality and become part of the future of our world.

Piero strongly desired this, and constantly followed this through with conviction, passion and dedication.

For a better future, we need young researchers of this kind.

European Fuel Cells and Hydrogen

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CAPRI, GRAN HOTEL QUISISANA
17 > 19 September, 2025

edited by
Viviana Cigolotti, Alessia Piccolo, Gabriele Loreti
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TOPICS

HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

Electrolysis (PEM, Alkaline, AEM, SOEC, PCC, MCEC) / Thermochemical & Photochemical Processes / Biological Hydrogen Production / Low carbon hydrogen from Fossil Fuels (e.g., SMR, CCS) / Nuclear Hydrogen Production / Hydrogen from Biomass and Waste

HYDROGEN STORAGE AND DISTRIBUTION

Solid Hydrogen Storage (e.g. metal hydrides, MOFs) / Gaseous Hydrogen Storage / Liquid and Cryo-Compressed Hydrogen Storage / Hydrogen Infrastructure (Pipelines, Tankers, Trucks) / Hydrogen Blending in Natural Gas Grids / Natural Gas Grid Transformation / Hydrogen Derivatives and Carriers / Hydrogen Refilling Stations / Challenges in Hydrogen Delivery Systems

FUEL CELLS TECHNOLOGIES

Fuel Cells: components, stack, system (PEMFC, SOFC, AFC, MCFC) / Fuel Cells for Transportation (Cars, Buses, Trucks) / Fuel Cells for Heavy Duty & Freight Transport (Trains, Aircraft, Marine) / Fuel Cells for Stationary Power Generation / Portable and Backup Power Applications / Materials Handling Application

HYDROGEN END-USE APPLICATIONS

Hydrogen for Industrial Processes (Steel, Cement, Chemicals) / Hydrogen as Energy Storage Medium (e.g. Hybrid Systems with Renewable Energy) / Sector Coupling and Power-to-X / Next-Generation Hydrogen Fuels (Power-to-fuel) / Hydrogen as a Decarbonization Pathway

HYDROGEN ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABILITY

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Social LCA / Techno-economic assessment (TEA) / Green Hydrogen and Carbon-Free Technologies / Water Use and Sustainability of Hydrogen Production / Hydrogen's Role in Achieving Climate Targets (Net-Zero Goals) / Hydrogen Hubs and International Trade / Hydrogen Valleys

HYDROGEN POLICY, MARKET, AND BUSINESS MODELS

National and Regional Hydrogen Strategies / Global Hydrogen Supply Chains / Economic Analysis and Market Forecasts / Public and Private Sector Investments / Hydrogen Pricing and Incentives / Hydrogen Safety Codes and Standards

HYDROGEN INNOVATION AND FUTURE TRENDS

Emerging Hydrogen Technologies / Breakthroughs in Catalysts, Electrodes, Membranes / Novel Systems Integration and Control / Digitalization and AI in Hydrogen Systems / Microbial and Bioelectrochemical Technologies

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Biomass to methanol by Breakthrough SOEC-based Process

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Keywords: syngas, co-electrolysis, Solid Oxide Cells

Abstract

This study explores the integration of solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOECs) in the process of methanol production, focusing on their performance with various fuel mixtures, which include water (H₂O), hydrogen (H₂), carbon dioxide (CO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), and methane (CH₄). The objective is to evaluate the cell's ability to operate at least at 500 mA/cm², enabling key reactions like water gas shift (WGS), steam methane reforming (SMR), and H₂O/CO₂ co-electrolysis. 25 cm² SOEC supplied by Elcogen were tested longer than 1000 h. The experimental results confirmed the SOEC's capability to meet the target requirements, although slow but steady degradation was observed.

Introduction: To enhance the contribution of renewables in the synthesis of methanol, an innovative cycle is proposed, wherein wood biomasses are gasified, and a SOEC stack is integrated downstream to tune the H₂/CO ratio of the reformat and achieve the optimal ratio of 2 [1, 2]. As SOECs are based on oxide ions transport, co-electrolysis of H₂O and CO₂ can be activated in parallel to high-temperature reactions such as SMR and WGS. The key challenge of the SOEC stack is the direct supply of a complex gas mixture whose target composition contains 4% CH₄, 15% H₂, 56% H₂O, 15% CO, and 10% CO₂. This raises critical questions regarding the cell's degradation, the extent to which various reactions take place, and the optimal operating point on the electrolysis curve, as the methanol synthesis line presents multiple waste heat streams that could be utilized by the SOEC if operated under endothermic conditions.

Objectives: The experimental investigation aims at understanding the kinetic and diffusive phenomena taking place in the electrodes, verify the SOEC's durability under target operating conditions, and assess how closely the system performs with respect to the expected conditions.

Material and methods: Single 5x5 cm² anode-supported cells (Elcogen) were tested, which featured a 290 μm Ni-YSZ fuel electrode, a 20 μm LSC (La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}CoO_{3-δ}) oxygen electrode, and a 7 μm YSZ electrolyte, with an additional 2 μm GDC (Gd_{0.1}Ce_{0.9}O_{2+δ}) interlayer. Performance

and durability experiments were conducted at 700°C with a Horiba-FuelCon C50 Evaluator test station. Polarization curves (I/V) were collected between Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) and 1.4 V in electrolysis mode, and from OCV to 0.7 V in fuel cell mode. Electrochemical impedance spectra were measured at OCV. The durability experiments were performed for over 1000 h with the target mixture, at different voltage levels (thermoneutral and below).

Results: The cell's performance was first evaluated in electrolysis mode with an 42/58 H₂/H₂O mixture fed to the fuel electrode, and air to the oxygen electrode. The fuel composition was then adjusted step by step to assess kinetics, until reaching the target mixture: CO₂ was introduced (10% vol), showing no impact as OCV remained near the Nernst potential of pure H₂O electrolysis. The introduction of CO (15% vol) slightly shifted OCV towards the WGS thermodynamic equilibrium. Further addition of CH₄ (4% vol), with 56% H₂O and 15% H₂ allowed to achieve the required target composition, and activating the SMR reaction. The ability to sustain the 500 mA/cm² current density required by the project was validated (Fig. 1A). A over 350 h durability study at thermoneutral voltage with the target composition (Fig. 1B) revealed slow, but steady degradation. Modification of the operative voltage allowed to achieve stable performance.

Conclusions: The experiments confirmed that the SOEC can operate at 500 mA/cm² with the cycle's target mixture. The I/V curve indicates that WGS, SMR, and water electrolysis characterize the SOEC's reactivity. Regarding durability, the SOEC degraded at thermoneutral voltage, but remained stable below.

Figure 1 – A) I/V curve 0.6 NI/min F.E. and 1.50 NI/min O.E. B) Durability experiment

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